

Conductance study of ion solvation in DMSO, MeOH and DMSO-MeOH mixtures at 25°

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Solvation behavior of Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Ag^+ and NO_3^- ions has been studied from the conductance measurement of solutions of LiNO_3 , NaNO_3 , KNO_3 , AgNO_3 and Bu_4NNO_3 in DMSO-MeOH mixtures. The data have been analyzed in terms of limiting molar conductivity (Λ_0) and ion-association constant (K_A) using a least-squares computer program of the Shedlovsky conductivity model. The limiting ionic molar conductivity (λ_0^\oplus) has been calculated on the basis of Ph_4PBPh_4 assumption; $\lambda_0^\oplus(\text{Ph}_4\text{P}^+) \equiv \lambda_0^\oplus(\text{Ph}_4\text{B}^-)$ and effective ionic radii (r_i) calculated using empirical modification of the Stokes' model. The r_i results are compatible with K_A values. An obviously typical difference in selective solvation for cations, Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ and Ag^+ is observed. Weak preferential solvation of NO_3^- by MeOH is reflected over the entire solvent composition range, which is found to be in contrast to the solvation of ClO_4^- in DMSO-MeOH mixtures.

In our earlier communication¹, we reported the results on ion solvation in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO)-methanol (MeOH) mixtures from the conductance and viscosity studies of the salts of perchlorates of alkali and silver metals. In the present work, we report the conductance study of the nitrates of these salts in DMSO-MeOH mixtures. Owing to different size and shape of anions, NO_3^- and ClO_4^- they appear to undergo interactions with solvent to different extent. Moreover, since cations are highly solvated in dipolar aprotic solvents² and anions are solvated in both dipolar aprotic and protic solvents², it is of interest to make a preliminary attempt to investigate ion solvation (both cation and anion) in conjunction with ion-association in DMSO-MeOH mixtures where DMSO is a dipolar aprotic solvent and MeOH is a protic solvent.

Results and Discussion

Molar conductivities of Bu_4NNO_3 , LiNO_3 , NaNO_3 , KNO_3 and AgNO_3 were determined in DMSO, MeOH and DMSO-MeOH mixtures containing 10.01, 20.03, 30.01, 39.98, 50.02, 60.10, 70.07, 80.10 and 90.04 mol% MeOH in the concentration range of $4-60 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} at $25 \pm 0.05^\circ$. The conductance measurements of KNO_3 could not be done in pure MeOH due to its poor solubility in methanol.

The entire results were analyzed in terms of limiting molar conductivity (Λ_0) and ion-association constant (K_A) using a least-squares computer program of the Shedlovsky conductivity model³ that involves following set of equations :

$$1/AS = K_A C \Lambda_{\pm}^2 S / \Lambda_0^2 + 1/\Lambda_0 \quad (1)$$

$$S = [\beta(c\alpha)^{1/2}/2\Lambda_0^{3/2} + (1 + \beta^2 c \Lambda / 4 \Lambda_0^3)^{1/2}] \quad (2)$$

$$\beta = 0.8204 \times 10^6 \Lambda_0 / (DT)^{3/2} + 82.501/\eta_0 (DT)^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

$$\log f_{\pm} = -1.8246 \times 10^6 (c\alpha)^{1/2} / (DT)^{3/2} / 1 + 50.29 \times 10^8 R (c\alpha/DT)^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{and } \alpha = AS/\Lambda_0 \quad (5)$$

where the symbols have their usual significances³. Both Λ_0 and K_A values are reported in Table 1. However, the Shedlovsky conductivity model was chosen for the reason best described earlier⁴. Moreover, the standard deviation of Λ_0 values calculated from the standard deviation of indi-

Table 1. Values of Λ_0 ($\text{S cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) and K_A ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) for some electrolytes in DMSO, MeOH and DMSO-MeOH solvent system at 25°

MeOH mol%	LiNO_3		NaNO_3		KNO_3		AgNO_3		Bu_4NNO_3	
	Λ_0	K_A	Λ_0	K_A	Λ_0	K_A	Λ_0	K_A	Λ_0	K_A
0	38.2	11	40.7	12	-	-	42.7	-	38.6	-
10.01	44.3	14	46.0	13	48.0	16	47.2	20	43.3	11
20.03	48.7	20	50.6	22	52.0	25	51.6	19	46.6	10
30.01	52.6	32	56.2	30	57.0	31	56.4	19	50.5	11
39.98	57.8	41	61.6	39	61.6	41	60.0	20	55.7	12
50.02	64.5	28	66.9	25	68.7	32	68.1	20	63.3	13
60.10	70.2	19	73.7	20	72.2	28	74.9	20	69.2	14
70.07	77.6	10	82.6	12	84.0	16	83.5	18	77.8	-
80.10	84.6	-	89.3	12	92.8	10	93.8	16	85.9	-
90.04	91.4	-	98.1	-	103.3	-	102.6	-	94.0	11
100	101.2	-	107.6	-	113.8	-	113.2	-	100.9	-

vidual point does not exceed the experimental uncertainty ($\pm 0.2\%$) which showed a good applicability of this model. The physical properties such as dielectric constant and viscosity coefficient of the medium required for the analysis of the data were taken from the earlier work¹.

The K_A values (Table 1) of LiNO_3 , NaNO_3 , KNO_3 and AgNO_3 show a non-linear dependence on solvent composition. The K_A values for LiNO_3 , NaNO_3 , KNO_3 initially increase as MeOH is added upto ~ 40 mol%. Above 40 mol% MeOH, the K_A values of these salts tend to decrease. The K_A values of AgNO_3 on the other hand remain practically constant over the entire composition range of the solvent. This is found to be contrary to that observed in case of perchlorate salts¹ where the K_A values were almost negligible. The association behavior of the electrolytes in DMSO-MeOH mixtures can also be inferred from the dependence of effective ionic radii (r_i) values of the ions on solvent composition. The r_i values of the ions are determined using empirical modification of the Stokes' law,

$$r_i = 0.82/\lambda_i^0 \eta_0 + (0.0103 D + r_y) \quad (6)$$

where r_y is an adjustable parameter that depends upon the nature of the solvent⁵, it is taken to be equal to 0.118 nm for associated solvents and 0.085 nm for non-associated solvents. In case of the mixtures, the r_y value is estimated by interpolation between these two values, as suggested by Gill and Nording⁶. In present solvent system, since both the solvent components are associated⁶, the r_y value has been taken to be equal to 0.118 nm over the entire solvent composition. All other symbols have their usual significances⁵.

Thus, it is essential to resolve the Λ_0 value of the electrolyte into the ionic contribution. This has been achieved using the $\lambda^0(\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+)$ values obtained earlier¹ on the basis of Ph_4PBPh_4 assumption; $\lambda^0(\text{Ph}_4\text{P}^+) \cong \lambda^0(\text{Ph}_4\text{B}^-)$ and Kohlrausch's law. The λ_i^0 values for Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Ag^+ and NO_3^- ions thus obtained in DMSO-MeOH mixtures are shown in Table 2. The λ_i^0 values are found to be in good agreement (accuracy ± 0.5). A perusal of Table 2 reveals that the r_i values of Li^+ , Na^+ and K^+ initially decrease as MeOH concentration increases upto ~ 40 mol% in DMSO-MeOH mixtures. It is possible that these result are the manifestation of known ability of DMSO to accept hydrogen bonds⁷, and thus, the intermolecular interactions between DMSO and MeOH are strong enough to overcome the M^+ -DMSO interactions ($\text{M}^+ = \text{Li}^+$, Na^+ and K^+). This is found to be consistent with the variation of K_A with solvent composition; the K_A value increases upto ~ 40 mol% MeOH. As MeOH concentration is increased further, the r_i value of these cations shows a slight increase upto ~ 70 – 80 mol%

Table 2. Values of λ_i^0 ($\text{S cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) and r_i (nm) of various ions in DMSO, MeOH and DMSO-MeOH mixtures at 25°

MeOH mol%	Li^+		Na^+		K^+		Ag^+		NO_3^-	
	λ_i^0	r_i	λ_i^0	r_i	λ_i^0	r_i	λ_i^0	r_i	λ_i^0	r_i
0	12.2	0.50	14.7	0.45	16.0	0.42	16.4	0.41	26.3	0.32
10.01	15.2	0.47	17.6	0.43	19.4	0.40	18.5	0.41	26.3	0.32
20.03	17.6	0.46	20.4	0.42	21.6	0.41	20.8	0.42	30.8	0.33
30.01	19.2	0.47	23.4	0.42	24.1	0.41	23.0	0.42	33.0	0.34
39.98	21.8	0.47	26.0	0.42	25.9	0.42	24.7	0.44	35.6	0.34
50.02	24.6	0.48	27.0	0.45	28.3	0.43	28.1	0.44	40.1	0.35
60.10	26.7	0.49	29.9	0.45	32.5	0.43	31.3	0.44	43.2	0.36
70.07	29.1	0.50	33.3	0.46	35.8	0.44	35.3	0.44	48.6	0.36
80.10	31.0	0.52	35.3	0.48	39.6	0.44	40.5	0.44	53.3	0.37
90.04	34.3	0.53	39.7	0.48	44.5	0.44	45.5	0.44	57.8	0.38
100	40.2	0.52	46.0	0.47	52.5	0.43	51.5	0.43	61.2	0.39

MeOH; a region where self-association of the solvent components is disrupted the most⁸ due to strong intermolecular interactions. Beyond 40 mol% MeOH, as K_A value tends to decrease, it suggests a slight preferential solvation of Li^+ , Na^+ and K^+ by MeOH in DMSO-MeOH mixtures.

On the contrary, the r_i of Ag^+ remains practically constant upto ~ 30 mol% MeOH. At 40 mol% MeOH, the r_i of Ag^+ however increases slightly and remains constant with further addition of MeOH. Being a transition metal ion of d^9 electronic structure, Ag^+ undergoes specific ion-solvent interactions² with DMSO that superimpose electrostatic ion-dipole type of interaction and leads to preferential solvation of Ag^+ by DMSO in DMSO-MeOH mixtures. A similar conclusion is reached from the change in K_A value of AgNO_3 where the change in K_A value of Ag^+ with solvent composition is negligible.

Another striking feature (Table 2) is that the r_i value of NO_3^- increases almost linearly with increasing concentration of MeOH whereas the r_i value of ClO_4^- remained constant¹. Such a difference may be explained in terms of the solvation of NO_3^- by MeOH. Moreover, since NO_3^- is more easily polarised¹⁰ (by cation) than ClO_4^- , it seems that the polarization is mediated by the solvent sheath. Consequently, NO_3^- is relatively strongly solvated by MeOH.

Experimental

DMSO (A.R., SRL) and MeOH (A.R., Ranbaxy) were purified as described earlier¹. LiNO_3 , (A.R., SRL), NaNO_3 , KNO_3 and AgNO_3 (G.R., E. Merck) were dried in a vacuum oven for 24–28 h. Bu_4NNO_3 was prepared and purified as described in literature¹¹.

Conductance was measured by a NDC-732 conductivity meter operating at 1 kHz frequency. Two different conductivity cells were used as described earlier¹. As described

Note

earlier¹², cell constant of each cell was determined in an aqueous solution of KCl in the concentration range $2-90 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. All measurements were carried out in a water thermostat (MLW Baureihe U7°) at $25 \pm 0.05^\circ$. Mixtures of DMSO and MeOH were prepared by weight (accuracy $\pm 0.03\%$).

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